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Research Article

**NATURE AND FREQUENCY OF DENTAL CASES: AN OUT
PATIENT DEPARTMENT SURVEY AT HYDERABAD,
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Yousaf⁵, Iram Jamil⁶**¹BDS, M.Sc. (Operative Dentistry), Senior Registrar, Department of Dental Material,
Muhammad Dental College, Mirpurkhas, Sindh, Pakistan.²BDS, MDS, Assistant Professor, Oral and Maxillofacial Department, Bhattai Medical and
Dental College, MirpurKhas, Sindh.³BDS, FCPS trainee (Orthodontics), Liaquat University of Medical and Health Sciences,
Jamshoro⁴BDS, Lecturer operative dentistry, Liaquat College of medical and dentistry, Jamshoro⁵BDS, Dental Surgeon, Hyderabad, Sindh⁶MBBS, MCPS trainee (Pediatrics), General practitioner, Hyderabad, Sindh**Article Received:** November 2019 **Accepted:** December 2019 **Published:** January 2020**Abstract:**

Dental diseases are very common in all age groups and both genders are equally affected. Large varieties of conditions are seen in common practice ranging from dental caries, periodontitis, submucosal fibrosis and oral ulcers. Current study was conducted at government Taluka Hospital in Oct 2019 in Dental OPD both gender with no age limits were included in the study. There were 814 patients seen in one month most of them 505(62.04%) were dental caries, 250 (30.71%) were periodontitis, Oral ulcers were 51(6.27%) and 08(0.98%) were sub-mucosal fibrosis. 327(40.17%) were males while 487(59.83%) were females. Data was analyzed on SPSS version 22 for frequency and percentage determination.

Conclusion:

Dental carries were the most common problem in dental outpatient department with female proportion slightly more than males.

Key Words: Dental Caries, Periodontitis, submucosal fibrosis, Ulcers

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INTRODUCTION:

Media has played big role for spreading awareness about the dental health that consequently led to measures of prevention and early treatment and become ultimately the mainstay even in well developed countries while other developing nations are also striving to achieve for the same [1]. Every community is affected by the dental decay despite the fact that the oral diseases vary in their nature as well as severity in various communities [2]. The treatment protocols for the oral pathologies are usually decided according to severity of the diseases on first presentation of the patient but the factors responsible for such conditions need to be well evaluated for designing the preventive measures well before the development of such pathologies [3]. Dental diseases is not the story of recent age but infect they have very old history including dental caries along with periodontal disease which were thought to be an essential part of the global burdens regarding oral health, dental caries has been reported to be prevalent around 95% even in developed countries which remains untreated in 90% in the developing countries [4-6]. Every corner of the earth has reported dental health issues with Latin America being on top prevalent for these illnesses followed by Middle East and South Asia and China being the least probably due to advanced dental care approaches [7]. The current article is our dental outpatient department work which urged us to get it published for the frequency

and nature of various dental conditions being observed by us in this part of the land, the Sindh with a diverse populations from various cultural backgrounds with beetle nuts, gutka, Paan parag, mam puri, naswar and cigarette as the common and routine use items all of which are worst for oral and dental health. Hope this milder effort by us will further spread the awareness which ultimately stimulate certain preventive steps at community and government levels.

METHODOLOGY:

Patients were selected as consecutive sampling with gender discrimination and the information regarding biodata were obtained on OPD slips. Nature of the dental diseases and their frequency was calculated and presented in table form, while gender distribution was also calculated and represented by pie chart, SPSS version 22 was used for analysis purpose. The study was planned and executed at Taluka hospital Qasim abad , Hyderabad ,Sindh, Pakistan in Oct 2019.

RESULTS:

There were 814 patients seen in one month most of them 505(62.04%) were dental caries, 250 (30.71%) were periodontitis, Oral ulcers were 51(6.27%) and 08(0.98%) were sub-mucosal fibrosis. 327(40.17%) were males while 487(59.83%) were females (Table-1,Figure-1).

Figure-1: Gender distribution of patients seen in study

S. No	Diseases	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Dental caries	505	62.04%
2.	Periodontitis	250	30.71%
3.	Oral ulcers	51	6.27%
4.	sub-mucosal fibrosis	08	0.98%
5.	Total	814	100%

DISCUSSION:

Aamir MK et al(2015) reported slight female dominance in their study with 52% female and 48% male which is consistent to our finding where we found 59.83% females and 40.17% male[8]. Mosha et al(1994) also reported females to more affected by dental diseases than male which also falls consistent to our findings [9]. Singh SK et al(2014) in his study results from Tanzania also concluded results favoring our outcomes [10]. Shaikh IA et al (2014) in his Pakistan study in the Khairpur district reported higher frequency of dental problems among female in comparison to male counterparts which is too consistent what we found[11]. Study results as reported by Badar Set al (2012) inconsistent to our results [12]. Similarly Sarvana et al(2008) from Tamil Nadu, India also reported inconsistent results in terms of gender involvement[13]. Shaikh et al (2014) reported from Larkana, Pakistan inconsistent results [14]. Muhammad HK et al (2012) reported dental caries the top most dental problem followed by periodontitis which is also consistent with present findings [3].

CONCLUSION:

Dental caries were the most common problem in dental outpatient department with female proportion slightly more than males.

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